

Environment Quality, FDI and Economic Growth in Sub-Saharan Africa

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

ABSTRACT

The primary objective of this paper was to examine the dynamic interactions of foreign direct investments, environmental quality and economic growth among sub-Saharan Africa (SSA) countries. To test long-run relationship the study employed the Panel Vector Auto regression (PVAR) and Panel Vector Error Correction (PVEC) methods. Results from the empirical model indicated that, there existed a dynamic interaction between our variables. This dynamic relationship was observed to range between 13.1% - 32.8%. The paper recommends the governments in the region to come up with policies and regulations that will balance the environmental regulations and investment-friendly policies. By doing this the region will attract the foreign direct investment and improve the quality of the environment.

Keywords: FOREIGN DIRECT INVESTMENTS, ENVIRONMENTAL QUALITY, ECONOMIC GROWTH, ENVIRONMENTAL REGULATIONS

Introduction

The environmental quality is dependent on the interaction between inflow of capital from abroad and the rate of the economic growth. Over the years the emerging nations have been in the forefront to attract the foreign direct investments. This is because the developing nations suffer the problem of undercapitalization. With an aim of adopting the measures the SSA governments have put their focus on integrating their economies with other global economies, with an aim of influencing the capital inflow. This is meant to promote the economic development of the region so that African countries as they strive to attain the Millennium Development Goals (MDG), and in particular the sustainable development goal. The conditions of the environmental in recipient country are crucial in promoting the FDI inflow to any country. The environmental condition controls the amount of FDI inflows to a specific country. Therefore, to attract foreign investment, the governments of developing nations tend to undermine their environmental regulations through loose or non-compulsory supervision. More companies in many industries and many countries are expanding overseas through foreign direct

investment more than ever before. This is reflected in the increase in the amount of foreign direct investment flowing into countries in the region for the last few years. Similarly, foreign direct investment by multinational companies in most SSA countries have traditionally relied on the use and exploitation of natural resources, especially agriculture, minerals, and oil production.

Therefore, in the past few decades, all trends in environmental deprivation have accelerated. This degradation includes the deforestation, greenhouse gas emissions, and loss of biodiversity. The economic activities increase has promoted this mode of environmental destruction, in which the inflow of foreign direct investment has become the main contributor. The level of FDI in a country can bring structural efficiency, new growth, new, and make more environmental protection investment possible (1); however, the FDI is anticipated to lead to increased production as well as the consumption of polluting goods or expansion of industrial activities, thereby increasing greenhouse gas emissions. This always reveals the interactions between specific variables of this paper, especially in sub-Saharan African countries.

In the past few decades, intense and controversial issues in the literature in the field of environmental economics have generated numerous debates and empirical research, centered on the direction of the relationship among the environment and the economic growth (2) This discussion seems to be quite stable in the context of advanced economies, because a lot of research has been published in this area, but it has just aroused new interest in the emerging countries. The previous literature on the interaction between foreign direct investment, environmental quality and the rate of economic growth was mostly examined in single-country. Nevertheless, there exist numerous analyses on cross-country for the developed countries.

Research on this interaction that has emerged in emerging countries is concentrated in the Asian region. The aim of this research is to fill this gap. In this research, the panel vector autoregression and panel vector error correction methods were used to study the dynamic interaction between foreign direct investment, environmental quality, and economic growth in Sub-Saharan Africa.

The outline of this article is as follows; Section 2 will review the theoretical issues. The next section (3) will describe the methodology used in this article. The empirical results will be discussed in Section 4, the last section (5), will summarize the paper.

Theoretical Issues

There exist numerous literatures on economic growth, the country's foreign direct investment, as well as environmental quality. This literature is classified into three aspects. The first school of thought links the FDI and the rate of economic growth, in which FDI is proved to have a positive effect on the economic growth. Some people believe that foreign direct investment increase the capital accumulation of the host

economy, improve the efficiency of domestic owned companies through competition, changes in the technology. Often it is claimed that foreign direct investment yields the capital that supplement domestic investments and reduce unemployment, and in most cases is related to technology transfer thus enhancing the economic growth (3).

The country's economic and social conditions are key determinants of how the FDI will contribute to economic growth (4). There exist various researches that support the idea that FDI stimulate economic development (5.). (6) proposed that FDI is considered important to explain China's economic growth, and (7) is also the case, and he proposed a positive relation with some of the Latin American nations. The paper stated that inflow of FDI effect economic growth positively; however there exist an income threshold level. Above the threshold level, FDI has a positive effect on economic development and vice versa.

Nigeria's non-extractive FDI contributed to the country's economy positively (8) however, the overall impact was not significant. (9) found that FDI has a positive impact on economic development by local investment stimulation, human capital increase, and technology transfer promotion in the recipient country. However, some studies generally report that the impact of foreign direct investment on the growth of developing host countries is negligible or has a negative impact. If foreign direct investment in the form of profit repatriation causes a large amount of reverse flows, especially if resources are repatriated through transfer pricing and dividends and/or multinational corporations (TNCs) obtain substantive or other concessions from the host country. For example, (10) found that FDI penetration variables had little or no impact on industrial growth.

Similarly, (11) reported that the influence of level of FDI inflows on the medium-term economic growth of per capita income in a sample of 41 developing countries was not significant. In addition, (12) by applying the Engle Granger co-integration and error correction model to short-term dynamics, it considers the growth hypothesis that FDI leads to 28 developing countries. They found that there is neither long-term nor short-term link among FDI and economic growth in majority of countries.

The next aspect connects the level of FDI and the quality of the environment, and is called FDI-Environmental Relationship. To achieve better economic efficiency, the governments of emerging nations tend to destroy environmental problems via loosening or non-enforcement of supervision, hence endorsing the pollution safe haven hypothesis of these countries. This allows international companies to transfer their business to emerging nations. This is because this international firms needs to benefit from the lower costs of production. This concept is known as the industrial flight hypothesis.

The massive investments by multinational firms have over the time led to increase in the carbon emission in the negligence of the host country's environmental standards. (13,14) confirmed that foreign companies

doing business in emerging countries that do not have or enforce environmental rules have led to excessive emission of pollutants and degradation of the host country's environmental standards. (15) constructed a synchronization system (3SLS) based on the data of 28 provinces in China from 1992 to 2008, taking into account the impact of FDI on the environment of the home country (China). The FDI has a negative effect on environment that is FDI, increase pollution to recipient country. However, (16) believes multi-national company's investments abroad have advanced technology and better management practices which help them reduce environmental pollution.

The third aspect links the rate of the country's economic development and the degree of environmental pollution. The previous literature shows that the level of environmental degradation increases with the development of the country, that is, economic growth leads to a decline in environmental quality. But when income exceeds the threshold, pollution levels decrease. This is a proportion is discussed by the Kuznets curve. Recent research by (17) that in six Central American economies, energy consumption is positively correlated with carbon dioxide emissions. However, when (18) considered causality, they found that there is a long-term causal relationship between levels of energy consumed, CO₂ emitted and the rate of economic growth.

The link between environmental degradation and foreign direct investment as discussed in the three dimensions above reveals a dynamic interaction, because any variable can drive other variables. There has been a lot of research interest in this relationship, but most of this type of work is not located in Africa. (19) used co-integration analysis and vector error correction models in their research to examine the short-term as well as long-term relationships between China's and India's economic growth, foreign direct investment, and the environment. Technology spillovers and foreign direct investment inflows play a key role in determining the short-term and long-term movements of economic growth. However, both short-term and long-term perspectives, the inflows of FDI from both countries have adverse effects on environmental quality.

In addition, if FDI is considered as a dependent variable, (20) finds that there is a long-term relationship between Malaysia's economic growth, foreign direct investment and energy pollutants. Similarly, (21) used panel cointegration to study the impact of economic growth and FDI on environmental degradation using data from the BRIC countries. Their research supports the long-term link between FDI, environmental pollutants and rate of economic growth. (22) showed that the rate of economic growth in developed countries has reduced the growth of energy emissions, but the environmental quality of developing economies is deteriorating in the process of economic growth. He uses the ARDL boundary test method to study how the environment is related to economic growth. He added that increasing energy demand is the main factor in energy emissions, while foreign direct investment has minimal impact on carbon dioxide emissions.

In the case of Nigeria, (23) found that FDI has a significant negative impact on per capita carbon emissions (CO₂); on the other hand, financial development indicators have positive effects on carbon emissions. This research was carried out in a single country in SSA. However, this research did not consider interactions because only two empirical variables dominate the research. (24) investigated the correlation between economic liberalization, growth and the quality of environment in Nigeria from 1970 to 2012.

This research considers the direction of causality between variables, and discovers the causal relationship from trade intensity to environmental quality; foreign direct investment on quality of the environment; the impact of per capita gross domestic product (GDP) on quality of the environment; and per capita GDP Contribution to FDI. The research was done in a single country; however, the research failed to consider the dynamic interactions between the specified empirical variables.

Evidence from various research works on dynamic interaction between foreign direct investment and quality of environmental shows both positive and negative effect. There is also very little literature on SSA sub-regions. This research adopts the panel method, which can make more reliable estimates by using differences between countries and changes over time. The study is necessary because it will give an over view of environmental quality and suggest the policies that we deem effective.

Methodology

This research use data for 33 nations drawn from the SSA region. The data was from 1985-2018. The time series data was extracted from the World Bank, (25). The study used the following variables; the real per capita growth rate, net FDI inflow as a share of GDP, and carbon dioxide emissions.

The research used panel vector error correction mechanism (PVEC) and panel vector autoregression (PVAR) to estimate the short run and long run relationship between our variables. (26), considered the VAR models to be the best way to study impulse response functions and the dynamic interactions between variables. This is because the models provide information on variables shock. The VAR model allows empirical variables interaction with each other's past values in the regression with no theoretical structure about the estimator.

Panel VAR Model Specification

This study considered three empirical variables in our model equation. Energy consumption (EGC) was used as a control variable. This was in order to track the effects of FDI and carbon emission intensity (CO₂) to levels of economic growth. The study also, used four-variable to explore the dynamic link between the

actual per capita income (rpy), carbon emission density (CO2), net FDI inflow (fdi), and logarithm of energy consumption (EGC) in our PVAR model.

The vector $Y_{i,t}$ of the endogenous variables can be expressed as

$$Y_{i,t} = \Phi_0 + \Phi(l)Y_{i,t} + \mu_i + \varepsilon_{i,t} \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

where $l = 1,2,3 \dots n$ and $t = 1,2,3, \dots t_i$

$Y_{i,t}$ = endogenous variables of the (4x1) matrix

Φ_0 are the constant vectors

Φ_l is the polynomial operator for the lag of variables defined as;

$$\Phi(l) = \beta_1 l + \beta_2 l^2 + \beta_3 l^3 + \dots \dots \dots \beta_\delta l^\delta \dots \dots \dots (2)$$

$\beta_i = (4x4)$ coefficients matrix

$v_i =$ country specific fixed effects matrix

$\varepsilon_{it} =$ normality (idd) (4x1) matrix vector.

As this study assumed structural disturbances to be serially uncorrelated, this study specified the unrestricted PVAR model as;

$$Y_{i,t} = \begin{bmatrix} Lrpy_{i,t} \\ Lfdi_{i,t} \\ LCO_2 \\ LEGC_{i,t} \end{bmatrix}, \Phi_0 = \begin{bmatrix} \gamma Lrpy \\ \gamma Lfdi \\ \gamma LCO_2 \\ \gamma LEGC \end{bmatrix}, \Phi(l)Y_{i,t} = \begin{bmatrix} \beta_{i,t} & Y_{it} & \alpha_{it} \\ \beta_{i,t} & Y_{it} & \alpha_{it} \\ \beta_{i,t} & Y_{it} & \alpha_{it} \\ \beta_{i,t} & Y_{it} & \alpha_{it} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} Lrpy_{i,t} \\ Lfdi_{i,t} \\ LCO_2 \\ LEGC_{i,t} \end{bmatrix} + \varepsilon_{i,t} = \begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon Lrpy_{i,t} \\ \varepsilon Lfdi_{i,t} \\ \varepsilon LCO_2 \\ \varepsilon LEGC_{i,t} \end{bmatrix} \dots (3)$$

Where:

$Lrpy_{i,t} =$ Log of real per capita income

$LCO_2 =$ Log of carbon emission

$LEGC_{i,t} =$ Consumption per capita

$Lfdi_{i,t} =$ Net inflow of foreign direct investment (%GDP)

The system of equations in a single equation form is described as:

$$\begin{bmatrix} Lrpy_{i,t} \\ Lfdi_{i,t} \\ LCO_2 \\ LEGC_{i,t} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \Phi \\ \Phi \\ \Phi \\ \Phi \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} \beta_{i,t} & Y_{it} & \alpha_{it} \\ \beta_{i,t} & Y_{it} & \alpha_{it} \\ \beta_{i,t} & Y_{it} & \alpha_{it} \\ \beta_{i,t} & Y_{it} & \alpha_{it} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} Lrpy_{i,t-p} \\ Lfdi_{i,t-p} \\ LCO_{2i,t-p} \\ LEGC_{i,t-p} \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon Lrpy_{i,t} \\ \varepsilon Lfdi_{i,t} \\ \varepsilon LCO_{2i,t} \\ \varepsilon LEGC_{i,t} \end{bmatrix} \dots (4)$$

PVAR was used to estimate equation 4.

The Model Specification

The VEC model is a hybrid of VAR model in discussed in Section above. The VEC model is used to best estimate the cointegrated VAR with non-stationary time series to estimate the short-term interaction between macroeconomic variable from the cointegration (long-term) equation. What makes the VAR model different from the VEC models is that, the VAR model includes the ECM term. This error term is used to forecast the convergence speed of short run equilibrium emanating from the long run equilibrium or deviation from long-term equilibrium, because the cointegration can be viewed in the long run.

If there is one-cointegration equation, the VEC model can be estimated together with ECM. The estimated Panel VECM arising from the $Y_{i,t}$ can be expressed as;

$$\Delta y_t = \alpha + \sum_{l=1}^{p-1} \phi_l \Delta y_{i,t-l} + \pi y_{i,t-1} + \varepsilon_t \dots \dots \dots (5)$$

The Δ is the equation differencing such that $\Delta y_t = y_{i,t} - y_{i,t-1}$;

$y_{i,t}$ = (nx1) column vector of endogenous variables

α = (nx1) vector of constant coefficients

ϕ and π = coefficient matrices

π = impact matrix, depicts the long – run relationships.

The Vector Error Correction expressed below:

$$\Delta Lrpy_{t-1} = \alpha_1 + \sum_{i=1}^{\rho} \beta_{j1} \Delta Lrpy_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^{\rho} \gamma_{j1} \Delta LFDi_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^{\rho} \phi_{j1} \Delta LCO_{2t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^{\rho} \alpha_{j1} \Delta LEGC_{t-1} + K_1 ECM_{t-1} + \varepsilon_1 \dots \dots \dots .6$$

$$\Delta LFDi_{t-1} = \alpha_2 + \sum_{i=1}^{\rho} \beta_{j2} \Delta Lrpy_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^{\rho} \gamma_{j2} \Delta LFDi_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^{\rho} \phi_{j2} \Delta LCO_{2t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^{\rho} \alpha_{j2} \Delta LEGC_{t-1} + K_2 ECM_{t-1} + \varepsilon_2 \dots \dots \dots .7$$

$$\Delta LCO_{2t-1} = \alpha_3 + \sum_{i=1}^{\rho} \beta_{j3} \Delta Lrpy_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^{\rho} \gamma_{j3} \Delta LFDi_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^{\rho} \phi_{j3} \Delta LCO_{2t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^{\rho} \alpha_{j3} \Delta LEGC_{t-1} + K_3 ECM_{t-1} + \varepsilon_3 \dots \dots \dots 8$$

$$\Delta LEGC_{t-1} = \alpha_4 + \sum_{i=1}^{\rho} \beta_{j4} \Delta Lrpy_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^{\rho} \gamma_{j4} \Delta LFDi_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^{\rho} \phi_{j4} \Delta LCO_{2t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^{\rho} \alpha_{j4} \Delta LEGC_{t-1} + K_4 ECM_{t-1} + \varepsilon_4 \dots \dots \dots 9$$

$ECM_{t-1} = \text{error correction term,}$

$\varepsilon_t = \text{residual.}$

If the estimated coefficient in our model is significant, they indicate the possibility of the re- equilibrium where the short-term dynamics is are represented by difference term coefficient.

The matrix representing the vector error correction models can be expressed as:

$$\begin{bmatrix} Lrpy_{i,t} \\ Lfdi_{i,t} \\ LCO_{2i,t} \\ LEGC_{i,t} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \alpha_1 \\ \alpha_2 \\ \alpha_3 \\ \alpha_4 \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} B_{j1} & \gamma_{j1} & \theta_{j1} & \lambda_{j1} \\ B_{j2} & \gamma_{j2} & \theta_{j2} & \lambda_{j2} \\ B_{j3} & \gamma_{j3} & \theta_{j3} & \lambda_{j3} \\ B_{j4} & \gamma_{j4} & \theta_{j4} & \lambda_{j4} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} Lrpy_{t-1} \\ Lfdi_{t-1} \\ LCO_{2t-1} \\ LEGC_{t-1} \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} K_1 \\ K_2 \\ K_3 \\ K_4 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} ECM_{t-1} \\ ECM_{t-1} \\ ECM_{t-1} \\ ECM_{t-1} \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} \mu Lrpy \\ \mu Lfdi \\ \mu LCO_2 \\ \mu LEGC \end{bmatrix} \quad (10)$$

This study estimated the equation 10 using the panel vector error correction. This was meant to confirm the dynamic link between the variables; the rate of economic growth, the quality of the environment and foreign direct investment.

Techniques used in estimating the model

Cointegration

According to various scholars such as ((27); estimating the regression with non-stationary data would yield a false output. Nevertheless, (28) in his study indicated that it is possible to estimate the model even when using non-stationary data. In this case, the variables are called cointegration and there will be no spurious regression problems.

To estimate the cointegration equation it is necessary to have non-stationary variables. In order to test for the stationarity of the variables this study conducted a unit root test. Thus, the study performed the panel unit root test. In economic modeling the use of cointegration is to check the variables long run relationship. In order to find if the variables have a long run relationship the study conducted the Johansen Cointegration test. The study employed the AIC to select the lag length.

Error Correction Analysis Procedure

In the countries selected by SSA, environmental quality, FDI and economic growth were co-integration, and it is necessary to avoid misinterpretation of the results of co-integration. Without any theoretical basis, it is necessary to derive the existence of cointegration equation does not imply that variables have a long-term equilibrium in the VAR system. We can study this relationship by carrying out an examination of the short-term and long-term relationships between the variable sets in the VECM. This is the result of widespread debate in the econometric literature, that is, it is best to check the cointegration non-stationary sequence in the VAR model under the VEC model to determine the long-term cointegration relationship, the short-term balance adjustment mechanism, and the adjustment speed.

Variance Decomposition and the Impulse Response Function

The existing literature have pointed out that in the case of a vector autoregressive model, it is difficult to explain a single short-term adjustment coefficient from the error correction model. Based on this view, the dynamic characteristics of the model are analyzed by using the method of variance decomposition (VD) and impulse response function (IRF). The impulse response functions method indicates the variables magnitude and direction of standard deviation (SD), and how these variables affect the other system variables over a period of time.

The forecasted error variance decomposes a proportion of the motion attributed to its impact in the measurement sequence to distinguish it from the motion attributed to the impact of additional variables. The FEDV method is used to analyze the effect of a variable Y in terms of variance resulting from the shock of Z. the FEDV usually indicate the contribution of the innovation resulting from the shock of the included variables. This study will use the FEDV to examine the dynamic relationship between the economic growth, FDI and the quality of the environment in the SSA region.

Estimation results and discussion

This study used three stages to carry out the econometric model. First the study examined the stationarity of the variables via the panel unit root. Then the study carried out the cointegration test in order to examine the long-term equilibrium relationship. Lastly this research elaborated the dynamic relationship between the Economic growth, FDI and the quality of the environment.

Unit root test

One of the requisites of the cointegration is the data stationarity. This research used the panel unit root testing. The table shows the unit root test of all the variables.

Table 2: Unit -Root Test

Variable	Levin, Lin and Chu (t-stat)	Im, Pesaran & Shin(W-sta)	ADF Fisher (Chi-sq)	P.P. Fisher (Chi-sq)	Level of Stationarity
GDP*	-16.7437	-17.6501	476.092	544.139	1
GDP**	-17.6789	-21.2712	484.199	735.901	1

FDI*	-2.2216	-5.16128	254.276	266.857	0
FDI **	-6.2538	-7.27837	268.486	276.272	0
CO2 *	-27.7274	-26.8380	786.925	870.649	1
CO2**	-27.3323	-27.9346	802.112	1488.65	1
EGC*	-24.2586	-24.5415	515.250	540.492	1
EGC**	-21.8744	-23.3618	496.830	741.760	1

* Intercept; ** Linear- Deterministic Trend; 0-Stationary at Level; 1- Stationarity at first difference.

With the exception of foreign direct investment, almost all tested variables are non-stationary at level ($p < 0.05$). This means time series variables are unstable and non-mean regression, which may make the model estimation structurally unstable. After the first-order difference, only three variables produce stationarity. The results indicated that variables were I (1). Thus, gave us the way forward to carry out a panel cointegration test.

Cointegration Results for the panel test

According to the findings in Table 2, after the first difference, almost all variables of interest have been introduced into stationarity, so the cointegration test statistics determine whether there is a long-term relationship between the relevant variables in the specified model.

This study used the method of Johansen Cointegration because it is heterogeneous and dynamic in nature. Table 3 below shows a summary of the results.

Table 3: Cointegration Results for the panel test

R	Max. Eigen Statistic		Trace Statistic	
R=0	393.3***	0.0000	466.6***	0.0000
R≤1	159.5***	0.0000	186.0***	0.0000
R≤2	73.26***	0.0005	80.56***	0.0001
R≤3	52.00**	0.0467	52.00**	0.0467

1% = ***, 5% = ** significance levels

Source: Author's Computation

The test for null hypothesis (no cointegration) between the empirical variables at the 1% and 5% significance level is rejected. The result shows that there is at least one cointegration vector. This means that the empirical variables used were co-integrated, indicating that there is a long-term feedback effect on the short-term dynamics of a particular model. The meaning of cointegration is that any variable can be used as a policy variable

Panel Vector Error Correction (PVEC) Dynamic Interaction Analysis

This section establishes a co-integration relationship between the quality of the environment, FDI and economic growth, and studies the dynamic interaction between environmental quality, FDI inflows, and

economic growth during the review period. This is examined using the short-term and long-term link between the variable sets in the VECM.

The cointegration test indicated that the time series data was cointegrated at level 4. Following this result we estimated the VEC model using the 4 lags. As indicated in the previous literature, in the case of a vector autoregressive model, it is challenging to interpret the results in the panel vector error correction model, thus this study considered the use of IRF and FEDV. The PVEC estimation results are listed in Table 4.

Table 4: Results of Estimated Vector Error Correction

Cointegration Eq:	CointEq1			
LOG(C02(-1))	1.000000			
LOG(RPY(-1))	22.19671 [1.00403]			
LOG(EGC(-1))	64.29119 [1.61229]			
FDI(-1)	32.58985 [5.53283]			
C	-345.5497			
Error Correction:	D(LOG(C02))	D(LOG(RPY))	D(LOG(EGC))	D(FDI)
CointEq1	0.000150 [1.18786]	7.87E-05 [3.84949]	1.75E-05 [0.88569]	-0.006456 [-4.12703]
R-squared	0.199560	0.249131	0.054180	0.302224
Adj. R-squared	0.171846	0.223134	0.021433	0.278065
F-statistic	7.200746	9.582893	1.654487	12.50965

Figures in parentheses are t-statistics

It can be seen that the long-term estimation model shows that the impact of FDI inflows and per capita income on carbon dioxide emissions is positively significant. The long-term net FDI inflow to the region has a significant positive impact on the growth of carbon emissions. As environmental policies are not so strict, the argument that foreign direct investment introduces heavily polluting intensive production processes into less developed countries may support this. This means that with the increase in FDI inflows in this sub region, the growth of pollution density will increase in the long run. This is consistent with as indicated by previous scholars i.e., (29).

The results show that in long run, there is a positive impact of per capita income on growth of carbon emissions. This means that an increase in the output is directly related to deterioration of the environmental quality. This result is consistency with previous literature such as those of (30). The results reveal the long-term deteriorating effects of FDI inflows and economic growth. This indicates long-term and positive impact

of FDI inflows and per capita income on the growth of the carbon dioxide emissions. This causes the deterioration of the quality of environment SSA region.

The error correction term (ECT) is used to explain long-term equilibrium speed. The equilibrium requirement is negative and less than 1. It reflects the adjustment speed from the short-term distortion of environmental quality to the long-term equilibrium in response to policy effectiveness. The result of the ECT indicates that the FDI had the expected sign while the other variables in the model had a positive effect. In addition, the values of energy consumption and per capita income were greater than 1. The empirical results indicate that the region is achieving the long-term equilibrium of the growth rate of carbon emissions; this is despite the existence of short-term distortions. This is a clear indication that the regulations on the environmental quality and standard are yet to be fully implemented.

FDI inflows in the selected nations adjustment speed was relatively moderate. The long-run rapid response of carbon emissions growth rate to the policies related to the macroeconomic have an effect on the region FDI net inflow. This implies that the rate of carbon emissions within the region quickly reaches equilibrium. Nevertheless, the speed of adjustment for the quality of the environment is explosive similar to the per capita income. This is a clear indication that the policy related to variables will have an explosive impact on the long-term equilibrium state of carbon emissions in the countries selected by SSA.

Panel impulse-response analysis

To track the endogenous variable shock the paper used impulse response function (IRF). The impulse response function diagram showing the effect direction consistent with the estimated sign is shown in Figure 1 below:

Figure 1: Results for Impulse Response Function (IRF)

The environmental quality (proxed by the rate of carbon dioxide emission) was considered in the first panel. This was in order to capture the effect of other variables in the model. The results show that the impact from the innovation of carbon emission has a positive impact on the actual carbon dioxide emissions. For our case the actual carbon dioxide emissions was represented by environmental quality. After the first quarter the trend assumed positive values. This positive trend was observed throughout the period under the study. Therefore, in the short, medium and long-term operations, unexpected changes emissions are found to hike the actual pollution in the sub region. Innovation in carbon emissions may be expansive in all time frames.

The impact on actual per capita income was observed to have positive impact on emission resulting from the actual carbon dioxide in selected nations. Therefore, whether it is in the short, medium or long term, innovations in real per capita income will increase SSA's carbon dioxide pollution. Similarly, shocks arising from the FDI had positive impact on emissions arising from the carbon dioxide gas in the short, medium and long term. Therefore, innovations in foreign direct investment inflows will increase carbon dioxide emissions in SSA countries.

Based on the perspective of the second panel, there was positive impact of real per capita income (rpy) and foreign direct investment on real per capita income. This effect was observed in the short, the medium and the long term. Considering model endogenous factors, the SSA may expansionary actual per capita income in the

short, medium and long term. Both the medium and long term, the impact of carbon emissions also shows a crowding out (negative) impact on the actual per capita income.

The innovative hypothesis of carbon emissions is negative from the 5th period to the remaining time. Therefore, an increase in per capita carbon emissions means that a decrease in environmental quality will reduce the region's actual per capita income. Both the medium- and long-term impact carbon emissions are anticipated to bring about the contradictory effect on the actual per capita income. As a result, the increase in the per capita income would be a good idea if the region would put more efforts in raising the FDI levels while at the same time reducing the levels of emission that is expected to come with it.

The research 3rd panel considered the reaction that foreign direct investment (FDI) would have as a result of changes in other empirical variables in the model. FDI shocks or innovations will have the positive impact on the actual influx of FDI in the SSA's. The shock arising from the FDI is anticipated to yield expansionary influence on the influx of the FDI both in the short, medium and long term.

Similarly, unexpected changes in real per capita income show the expansion effect of actual inflows. This estimate assumes a positive value from the first period to the end of the 24th period. Therefore, the innovation

Of per capita income have a short-, medium-, and long-term positive impact on the influx of FDI from sub-Saharan African countries.

In addition, results indicate the impact of emissions will have a negative impact on FDI influx in SSA. Innovations in emission intensity will have a short-term positive impact on the influx of the regions level of FDI. This means that in order to raise FDI inflows in the short term, loose environmental supervision should be adopted to encourage polluting foreign industries, rather than strict environmental policies. This supports the pollution safe haven hypothesis. However, the estimated trend value is assumed to be negative in the 4th period and continues to expire at the end of the period. Therefore, the mid- to long-term impact of shocks on carbon emission intensity is negative for FDI flowing into SSA countries. In the medium and long term, innovations in carbon emission intensity will have a contradictory effect on FDI inflows to countries selected by SSA.

The Variance Decomposition Analysis

To reveal interaction between our empirical variables in the region this study developed the variance decomposition. The model was generated from the Panel VAR; the model describes the contribution of the shock to our explanatory variable. The standard error of the variance decomposition is the prediction error of the variable within a given prediction range. The results of the variance decomposition were is presented in the table below.

Table 5: Forecast Error Panel Variance Decomposition Results
LOG (C0₂)

Period	S.E.	LOG(C0 ₂)	LOG(RPY)	LOG(EGC)	FDI
1	0.259591	100.0000	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000
4	0.367859	96.54357	1.260232	1.566220	0.629982
8	0.485640	91.64718	1.953903	2.427640	3.971276
12	0.587368	86.26993	2.407171	3.063573	8.259325
16	0.679521	81.31401	2.728000	3.564795	12.39320
20	0.763875	77.08684	2.959102	3.990682	15.96338
24	0.841419	73.57892	3.129268	4.371157	18.92066

Variance Decomposition of FDI

Period	S.E.	FDI	LOG(C0 ₂)	LOG(RPY)	LOG(EGC)
1	3.242764	100.0000	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000
4	4.057216	97.89652	0.968272	0.778700	0.356506
8	4.544709	97.34392	0.905476	1.193863	0.556740
12	4.749010	97.11852	0.885241	1.326889	0.669349
16	4.838011	96.96952	0.908118	1.372197	0.750162
20	4.877299	96.85493	0.945534	1.386394	0.813143
24	4.894893	96.75867	0.987507	1.389652	0.864170

Variance Decomposition of LOG(RPY)

Period	S.E.	LOG(RPY)	FDI	LOG(EGC)	LOG(C0 ₂)
1	0.044505	100.0000	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000
4	0.122472	98.66747	0.405014	0.911279	0.016235

8	0.200345	91.72134	6.579049	1.624314	0.075301
12	0.270874	82.45736	15.36258	2.007266	0.172795
16	0.337324	74.57981	22.87165	2.265320	0.283222
20	0.399386	68.56442	28.56104	2.476060	0.398478
24	0.456816	64.05519	32.75782	2.669756	0.517227

The panel table above in the first portion describes the error variance of the emission density as explained by the innovation. The key variables in determining the changes in CO₂ emissions include the capita income, FDI net influx in region, and levels of energy consumption. Carbon dioxide emissions fell from 100% in the first quarter to 73.60% in the 24th quarter. Over time, the value of region's GDP had an increase from 0.00% to 1.950% in the first quarter to eighth quarter respectively. This figure increased to 3.130% in the 24th quarter. The EGC scale increased to 1.570% from 0.00% in the first quarter to in the fourth quarter, and then further increased to 4.370% in the 24th quarter. The scale of FDI increased from 0.00% in the first quarter to 3.970% in the 8th quarter and further rise to 18.9% in the 24th quarter.

The impact on CO₂ explains the largest proportion of its own change in the short term. In the long run, FDI is more likely to explain CO₂ changes. In other words, the long-term impact of FDI inflows on CO₂ is greater than that of RPY and EGC. This means that as the governments of SSA countries focus on attracting foreign direct investment policies, the environmental quality of the region continues to deteriorate. Strengthen the quality assessment of foreign direct investment inflows to ensure that the environmental conditions in the sub-region are improved.

The panel above in the second portion describes the error variance of the FDI influx for the selected countries in the region. The error variance is explained by endogenous variables innovation shocks. FDI and RPY are the key variables that determine changes in FDI. The FDI scale variance was 100% to 96.76% between the first quarters to 24th quarter. An innovation in FDI inflows from the region was observed to have a higher potential with an aim to raise the actual FDI inflows. The RPY range of raised from the 0.00% to 1.39% in the first quarter to 24th quarter. Over time, the degree of carbon dioxide had an increase from the 0.00% to 0.97% in the first quarter to fourth quarter, this figure had a further hike to 0.99% in the 24th quarter.

In addition, EGC the size rose from 0.00% to 0.36% in the first quarter to fourth quarter, the figure raised further to 0.86% in the 24th quarter. Innovation in income per capita is anticipated to have a greater potential to raise the regions level of FDI influx and also has greater potential. Compared with environmental variables, the impact of SSA selected countries on real GDP growth. The shock related to the influx of FDI explains the proportion of its own changes in the short term. From the results the per capita income had a potential to forecast the changes in the long-run FDI inflow.

Third panel presents the proportion of the error variance in the actual income per capita of the countries by the SSA. This was explained by the endogenous variable's innovation. Three important that can be used in determining the changes in actual income per capita includes the FDI, RPY, and EGC. The RPY range had a variance from 100% to 64.1% in the first quarter to 24th quarter. Compared with other variables, the innovation of per capita real income had a greater potential to raise income real per capita. The FDI scale raised from 00.0% to 6.58% in the first quarter to eighth quarter and 32.76% in the twenty-fourth quarter.

The EGC scale raised from 0.00% in the fourth quarter to 2.67% in the 24th quarter. The scale of CO₂ did not increase significantly from 0.00% in the first quarter to 0.08% in the eighth quarter, and then to 0.52% in the 24th quarter. Compared with EGC and CO₂, innovation in FDI explains a larger proportion of changes in real GDP growth. This means that the governments should approve policies that can attract a large influx of FDI, because it affects real per capita income in the long term.

Conclusions and the Policy Implications

The primary objective of this paper was to examine the dynamic interactions of foreign direct investments, environmental quality and economic growth. This research use data for 33 countries drawn from the SSA region. The data was from 1980-2013. The empirical variables used in this study were first-order integrals, and the panel cointegration test results confirm that there is a long-term equilibrium in the empirical variables. The dynamic model result between FDI, environmental quality and the economic growth under the PVAR model showed a significant and positive impact in the short and long term.

Considering the models for the impulse response function and the variance decomposition, it is revealed that the included variables explain each other's changes in the sub-regions. These results confirmed the feedback effect between our empirical variables FDI, the quality of the environment and the economic growth in the SSA area. In selected SSA countries, the interaction between our empirical variables followed an expected pattern. The relationship depicted was that an increase in levels of FDI influx in the region was directly related to the region's growth rate of GDP; similarly, the increase in FDI inflow levels also had similar effects on the quality of the regions environment, on contrary the rise in the quality of environment did not increase the levels of FDI influx.

The improvement of environmental standard is observed to raise the GDP, and on contrary the rise in the rate of GDP did not improve the quality of the environment. We can attribute these effects to the lack of harmonization of regulations related to the environment. This scenario has an effect on the region as it can fuel the capital flight out of the region. Non-enforcement of laws and policies related to the environmental continues to make it possible for entrants to polluting industries. This negligence is seen as the leading cause of the environmental deprivation and increased productivity. In addition, loose economic policies allow profits and capital to be repatriated domestically; this inhibits the long-term positive impact of the FDI

inflows to the region and the improvements on the environmental quality. Therefore, countries in the region should put more focus on effectively adopting and implementing regulations that can attract and preserve foreign direct investment across the region and improve environmental quality with an aim of ensuring continued economic growth.

The article findings had important policy suggestions. For instant in order to generate the more economic growth in the region, the governments have obligation to mobilize foreign capital while at the same time protecting the environment. It is necessary to control environmental degradation and pollution caused by increasing production activities through appropriate policy combinations. Governments from all the countries need to strike a balance between the friendly-investment policies and the policies that will raise the standard of environmental. This will raise the level of foreign direct investment by countries in the region will become an investment to improve the environmental quality of the region.

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